

THE ROLE OF TECHNOLOGY IN ESL TEACHING

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ABSTRACT

Over through the preceding 50 years, informational technology has advanced in reaction to the demand for further effective methods to handle the rapidly rising amount and complexity of scientific consciousness. It incorporates the fields of computer programming, communications, and computer applications; it deals with the gathering, storing, retrieving, editing, and disseminating of content; and it has a benefit across both work and recreational pursuits. Most residents manage to be able to gain hands-on experience with software development approaches in a system marked by technical advancement and computer based interactions to circumstances at work and in broader society if we are to close the massive disparity between developing and developing countries and give our individuals the best possible opportunity to live and development in this current frontier.

Digital sector has traditionally grown to be a critical aspect of education both inside and outside of the classroom. Most language programs utilize technology a certain way. Innovation has been employed to aid and enhance language learning. Educators can modify teaching methods through the use of technology, which improves language acquisition. Technology's significance as a weapon to assist academics in facilitating teaching and learning for their students keeps growing.

The utilization of modern technology in teaching English as a second or foreign language is the main topic of this project. It covered several viewpoints that encourage English language students to enhance their learning abilities through using technology. In this document, the dictionary describes the terms "innovation" and "technology integration," discussed how technology is used in language classrooms, evaluated prior research regarding the application of technologies to enhance language learning abilities, and made some suggestions for how to use these innovations more effectively to help learners enhance their learning abilities. According to the literature study, efficient use of modern technologies enhances language learners' abilities to acquire new languages. Technology has always played

a significant role in the education and instruction process. It is a crucial component of the job of teachers since they can use it to aid students' learning.

The term "integration" is used when discussing how innovation is used in the classroom. It is time to reconsider the concept of incorporating technology into a course of study and focus on embedding the use of technology to help the cognitive development because technology is a part of how we live. In other words, from the outset of planning educational activities through the process of teaching and learning, technology becomes a crucial component of the learning opportunity and a serious component for educators (Eady & Lockyer, 2013). Regardless of the learners' backgrounds, enhancing their expertise and abilities in information technology gives parity of access.

Despite being raised in a highly technological environment, learners may not be adept technologists. However, simply giving people access to technology is insufficient. All students must gain meaningful innovation knowledge if they want to optimize their education (OECD, 2010). The investigator will investigate some of the key problems important when it comes to employing technology in the teaching and learning of English language skills in this recent review. These concerns include the following: the concept of software, its application in the curriculum, earlier research on its application in enhancing English language learning abilities, and suggestions for its application.

Technology is a useful tool for students. Implementing technology by students in the learning process is essential. For students to boost their actual usage of technology to develop their linguistic skills, educators should be role models for how to utilize technology to complement the program (Costley, 2014; McNamara, DePasquale, & Murphy, 2003). Automation can promote student collaboration. One of the key methods of instruction is cooperation. Students produce assignments collaboratively with one another and gain knowledge from one another by studying the work of their classmates (Keser, Huseyin, & Ozdamli, 2011). Technology use, according to Dawson, Cavanaugh, and Ritzhaupt (2008) and Pourhosein Gilakjani (2014), can establish an educational setting that is more focused on the student than the instructor, which results in beneficial changes. They stressed the use of computer technology to language instruction turns into a lively environment with purposeful assignments where students take ownership of their education. The use of information technology, according to Drayton, Falk, Stroud, Hobbs, and Hammerman (2010), implies a genuine learning opportunity that strengthens students' obligations.

Technology enables students to develop independently and to adopt appropriate behaviors. Students have identity thanks to their autonomous use of technology. Utilizing the internet, in accordance with Arifah (2014), boosts students' motivation. The usage of films in the classroom encourages students to engage with the material and broaden their understanding. When innovation is incorporated into the method of instruction through the use of a computer and the internet, students can gain knowledge substantively. Learning with technology helps students build their intellectual abilities. The proper blending of multimedia and instructional techniques is crucial to capturing students' interest in learning the English language. ICTs (information and communication technologies) can help in teaching and learning in several ways.

Initially, learners take an active part, which can aid in their memory retention. Secondly, follow up discussions provide more knowledge, allowing students to develop their independence. Ultimately, students' linguistic abilities can improve as a result of their capacity for analyzing new learner-based instructional resources (Costley, 2014; Tutkun, 2011). The shift from teacher-centered to learner-centered methodologies is a result of the usage of technology.

Instructors should act as guides and organizers for their students' learning, and this transformation will help students learn more (Riasati, Allahyar, & Tan, 2012). According to Gillespie (2006), utilizing technology fosters greater student participation in educational work. It helps kids learn new things and engage with materials like webinars. The increased cooperation between professors and students is one of the effects of employing technology in language lessons, according to Mouza (2008) and Sabzian, Pourhossein Gilakjani, and Sodouri (2013). When instructors invite students to assist them in the classroom, this can boost students' self-assurance. Students are given the chance to reaffirm their beliefs and acquired skills. Because they have had plenty of time to master technology while teachers focus on guiding the lesson, students can assist teachers in integrating it into the classroom. In a 2011 study, Lin and Yang looked at the possibility that wiki software could enhance students' writing abilities. Students were urged to sign up for a Wiki page where they would create lines, read the paragraphs of their mates, and respond. The learners said that one advantage of utilizing this kind of technology was the quick response they got.

According to the literature survey, technology use also has an essential function in 12 learners at the driver's licence own speed and fosters strong motivation in students for the efficient acquisition of language abilities. In addition, the report argued that language students should use technology to enhance their language proficiency since it fosters creativity in learners and offers them fun and engaging ways to learn the language. In conclusion, this literature review's findings demonstrated that technology fosters interaction between teachers and students, offers understandable input and output, makes learning and teaching more student-centered, encourages students' autonomy and builds their self-confidence, and boosts students' motivation to successfully learn a foreign language.

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